

MARKET EXPANSION STRATEGIES AND OPERATIONAL STABILITY OF BAKERY INDUSTRIES IN AKWA IBOM STATE

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of the study was to determine the influence of Market Expansion strategies and Operational Stability of bakery industries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study determined the influence of market research and product development on the operational stability of bakery industries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Two research questions were answered in the study, and two null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all 439 staff from bakery industries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. A questionnaire designed by the researcher was used for data collection. Cronbach's Alpha was used to compute internal consistency reliability. Simple linear regression was used to answer research questions and to test the null hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that the application of market research and product development have strong and significant influence on the operational stability of bakery industries in Akwa Ibom State. Based on the findings, the study concluded that market expansion has moderate and significant influence on the operational stability of bakery industries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study therefore recommended, among others, that owners and managers of bakery industries should endeavor to provide the necessary tools and facilities needed to achieve business growth and expansion, which is the ultimate goal of businesses. Products should be properly developed to have good market share to attract buyers, coupled with proper market research in order to have operational stability.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Any commercial activity which involves providing goods or services with a primary motive of earning profits is termed a business. The business concept, according to Patri et al. (2021), is the fundamental idea behind the business model, plan, vision, and mission, which are developed based on this concept. In addition to that, Putri et al. maintained that the business objective is what makes the business go on and conduct its activities in the long run. Business seems to be the bedrock of any country's economic development because it helps in improving the employment rate by providing jobs for both skilled and unskilled labour.

Any bakery company that is not considering market expansion strategy in its operation is planning to fail. Developing countries have always been behind in terms of economic growth. One of the reasons behind this difference, as opined by Tongus and Omar (2017), is the lack of proper market expansion and support for entrepreneurship and startups. Market expansion strategy plays a vital role in the economic growth of any country. Market expansion, as postulated by Gioli (2014), is the process of expanding and strengthening markets by increasing access to information, finance, and technology. A Market expansion strategy, according to Rundh (2015), is a business growth strategy that focuses on introducing existing products to a new market. Rundh further stated that businesses often use market expansion strategies to identify and develop new opportunities to sell their products in previously unexplored markets, which can also increase trade between one region and another. By expanding their markets, Ayal and Zif (2019) asserted that they can attract more foreign investment and export higher-value products, which can boost their economic growth and can lead to increased innovation.

As more bakery industries compete in the market, Ayal and Zif further maintained that they will be forced to find new ways to differentiate themselves from their competitors. Invariably, this can lead to the development of new products, services, and business models. In addition to this, Mbithi and Rambo (2015) opined that market expansion creates new employment opportunities, especially in the informal sector, which can help in reducing poverty and improving the living standards of the community. Rapoport (2015) supported that the most important reason one should use market expansion is to drive bakery sales. For instance, whether the baking industries sell extra bread or more, there would be an increase. These increases are evidence of business growth, and if the company is run correctly, profit increases. Therefore, to make a new bakery company successful, Rapoport further stated that it is important to define the target market and put an actionable plan in place to reach them. Developing a well-researched bakery marketing plan, according to Rundh (2015), allows the management team to pick a location for the business in the heart of ideal customers and create content that resonates with them.

Bakery industries have always been a beloved staple in communities around the world. But with changing times and evolving consumer preferences, Avila and Nurrani (2020) posited that there is a need for innovative approaches in the company. Other innovative bakery company ideas include gluten-free gourmet bakery, midnight bakery deliveries, bakery subscription box, virtual baking classes, health-focused bakery café, cultural fusion bakery, eco-friendly bakery, bakery food truck, and personalised baked goods. Healthier organic and gluten-free options are equally crucial to this business. However, on the part of the bakery company,

Patri et al. (2021) postulated that bakery industries' current state in the market is a thing of concern. Stiff competition, rise in the cost of ingredients, equipment, labour, seasonal fluctuation, sustainability concerns, changes in customers' preferences, rising ingredient costs, staffing issues, equipment maintenance, food safety regulations, marketing and branding, managing inventory, cash flow management, and food safety regulations are constantly evolving with the growing demand. These inadequacies, as supported by Okafor (2020), have affected the operational stability and profitability of bakery industries in Akwa Ibom State,

Nigeria. Failure to manage allergens and comply with labeling regulations, according to Oluwakemi (2017), results in negative feedback from customers and penalties imposed by regulatory agencies. This cannot only harm the reputation of the bakery industries but also result in financial losses. Raina (2024) confirmed that these problems will not allow the management to stay agile, innovative, and customer-focused in order to thrive in the competitive market. Raina added that the bakery industries face a lot of challenges such as product shelf-life management, food allergen management, supply chain delays, seasonal fluctuations in demand, and rising operation costs.

The bakery industries cannot operate without experiencing difficulties. Raina (2024) stated that it is important to create a perception of value for bakery products by highlighting their quality, freshness, and unique flavours. This can be achieved through effective branding, marketing, and communication strategies. Striking the right balance between costs, competition, and perceived value is crucial.

Product development is the complete process of bringing a new product to market, renewing an existing product, and introducing a product in a new market. It is the overall conception of developing the product to the end users. First and foremost, the market need must be identified, followed by researching the competition, proffering a solution, developing a product roadmap, and building a minimum viable product.

Statement of the Problem

The concern of the study is to examine the influence of market expansion on the operational stability of bakery industries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Establishing bakery industries in a place is a welcome development; expanding the firm is a blessing to the owner(s) and the community as baking items would be accessible to the people. However, many bakery industries in Akwa Ibom State have crumbled due to poor planning and inability to develop new products or conduct proper market research. Other challenges faced by owners and managers include, but are not limited to: high operating costs, stiff competition, seasonal fluctuation, quality control, marketing and branding, staffing issues, food safety, and regulation. Hence, there is need for expansion for operational stability to be achieved. The adoption of business expansion strategies is of immense benefit to bakeries by allowing them to increase their customer base, generate more sales, expand their market reach, improve brand awareness, and ultimately boost profitability by introducing new products, tapping into new customer segments, and optimising operations to meet growing demand, among others.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the influence of Market expansion on operational stability of bakery industries in Akwa Ibom, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine the influence of:

1. Market research on operational stability of bakery industries in Akwa Ibom, Nigeria.
2. Product development on operational stability of bakery industries in Akwa Ibom, Nigeria

Research Questions

1. What is the influence of market research on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

2. How does product development influence operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of market research on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of product development on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

The concept of a bakery company revolves around delicious and high-quality baked products to meet the needs and preferences of customers. This, according to Patri et al. (2021), typically involves a combination of baking skills, creativity in recipe development, and attention to detail in presentation. Key aspects for a bakery company concept, according to Gioli (2014), include product offering, quality ingredients, unique selling proposition, customer experience, marketing, and branding. Product offering means that a bakery company may specialise in a particular type of baked goods, such as artisan bread.

The product offerings, according to Patri et al. (2021), should be appealing to the target market and may include a variety of flavours, sizes, and styles to cater to different preferences. In support of this, Patri et al. stated that high-quality ingredients are essential for creating delicious baked goods that stand out from competitors, and premium ingredients can enhance the taste and overall quality of the products. For a unique selling proposition to differentiate itself in a competitive market, Raina (2024) buttressed the fact that a bakery company may have a unique selling proposition such as offering gluten-free or vegan options, using organic ingredients, or providing custom cake designs. This helps attract customers who are looking for something specific. Some key elements of business include customer experience, marketing, and branding.

Customer experience is to be providing excellent customer service, a welcoming atmosphere, and a visually appealing display of products can enhance the overall customer experience. Avila and Nurrani (2021) postulated that a bakery company may also offer seating areas for customers to enjoy their purchases on-site as well as online ordering and delivery options for convenience. In terms of marketing and branding, Avila and Nurrani added that effective marketing strategies such as social media promotion, collaborations with local businesses, and participation in community events can help increase brand awareness and attract new customers. Avila and Nurrani further stated that developing a strong brand identity through logo design, packaging, and consistent messaging can also establish a bakery company in the market. A bakery company is an establishment that helps the business produce and sell flour-based goods made in ovens such as bread, cookies, cakes, doughnuts, bagels, pastries, and pies.

Market Research and Operational Stability of Bakery industries

Market research is a crucial aspect of any business, and a bakery company is not an exception. A well-crafted marketing strategy can help a bakery company increase its customer base,

generate more sales, and establish a strong brand identity. Orji (2020) stipulated that market research is an essential part of product development and is crucial for the success of a bakery company for understanding customers' preferences, identifying market trends, assessing competition, determining pricing strategies, and identifying growth opportunities. Market research in the bakery industry, according to Onwubiko (2015), involves gathering and analyzing information about the market, customers, competitors, and company trends to make informed decisions and develop effective strategies. Onwubiko further posited that it must be conducted to identify customer needs, preferences, and trends, understand the target market, analyse competition, assess company trends, conduct customer surveys, pricing, and profitability, among others.

In terms of innovation, Reguia (2014) asserted that the bakery company should invest in research and development to create innovative products that offer unique features and benefits to customers. Reguia added that innovation can help differentiate products from competitors and attract more customers. Product quality, on the other hand, ensures that products meet high-quality standards to build customers' trust and loyalty. High-quality products, as postulated by Avila and Nurrani (2021), are more likely to generate positive word-of-mouth and repeat purchases. In pricing strategy, Sije and Oloko (2023) opined that implementing a competitive pricing strategy that reflects the value of the product and resonates with the target market is essential. Pricing products appropriately can help maximize revenue and profitability. In terms of customer feedback, it helps to understand their satisfaction levels and areas for improvement.

This feedback can equally be used to make necessary adjustments to products and customer experiences and develop effective marketing strategies to promote products and reach a wider audience. Various marketing channels, as asserted by Ibidunni (2010), should be utilized, such as social media, advertising, and partnerships, to increase product visibility and drive sales. Elements of market research include customer demographics, customers' preferences, competitor analysis, trends in bakery industries, location analysis, pricing strategy, marketing strategies, among others.

Avila and Nurrani (2021) maintained that market surveys should be conducted or focused on groups to gather information on customer preferences such as favorite flavours, types of baked goods, and dietary restrictions. This would assist in developing products that appeal to the target market. Elements of customer preferences include taste, variety, freshness, presentation, price, customer service, customization, health, and dietary considerations. In terms of taste, customers often prioritize the taste of baked goods, looking for fresh, flavourful, and high-quality products. Variety is also important; offering a diverse range of baked goods, including different flavours, types, and dietary options such as gluten-free or vegan, can cater to a wider customer base. In terms of freshness, Huttner and Arendt (2010) posited that customers generally prefer freshly baked goods that are made with high-quality ingredients. In terms of presentation, Huttner and Arendt added that the visual appeal of baked goods can greatly influence customer preference. Eye-catching displays and attractive packaging can attract customers. Freddie (2020) added that price is not left out in the process; customers often consider the price of baked goods when making purchasing decisions. Offering competitive pricing or value deals can attract price-conscious customers. Meanwhile, providing excellent customer service, such as being friendly, helpful, and attentive to customers' needs, can enhance the overall customer experience.

Moreover, gathering feedback from customers through surveys, interviews, focus groups, and social media helps in understanding their satisfaction levels, preferences, and suggestions for improvement. In terms of company trends, Ibidunni further posited that keeping track of

industry trends, technological advancements, regulatory changes, and economic factors is crucial for adapting to market shifts and staying ahead of the competition.

Market research in bakeries can face several challenges, according to Raina (2024), such as limited sample size, seasonal variations, competition, changing customers' preferences, cost constraints, limited resources, and data accuracy. In terms of limited sample size, Raina buttressed the fact that it can be difficult to gather a large enough sample size of potential customers to make statistically significant conclusions about market trends and preferences. Seasonal variation means that bakeries may experience fluctuations in demand based on seasons and holidays, making it challenging to accurately predict market trends throughout the year.

In terms of competition, Raina further stated that the bakery market can be highly competitive, with many established and new businesses vying for customers' attention. This can make it challenging to differentiate bakery industries and accurately assess market demand. In terms of changing customer preferences, Segarra (2019) posited that customer tastes and preferences can change rapidly, making it challenging to keep up with evolving trends and adjust product offerings accordingly. In terms of cost constraints, Orji (2020) opined that conducting comprehensive market research can be expensive, especially for small bakery companies with limited budgets.

This can limit the scope and depth of the research conducted. In terms of limited resources, small businesses may lack the resources, expertise, or time to conduct thorough market research, leading to potentially inaccurate or incomplete data. Solving market research problems in a bakery company involves conducting thorough research and analysis to understand the market, customers, and competition. Ibidunni (2010) stated some of the steps to solve market research problems in bakery industries. These include conducting marketing research, defining the problems, analysing the data, identifying opportunities, developing a strategy, implementing, and monitoring performance. By following these steps, Onwubiko (2015) opined that one can effectively solve market research problems in bakery industries and make informed decisions to drive growth and success.

Market research is an incredibly valuable tool for gathering information about a future bakery company. Onwubiko (2015) stated that market research consists of the systematic gathering of data about people and then analysing it to better understand what that group of people needs. Market research helps make solid business decisions, secure funding from investors, determine new business opportunities, and avoid business failures. Orji (2020) explained market research as the process of collecting vital information about a company, target audience, market, and competition.

However, Ibidunni (2010) posited that market research in a bakery company can face several challenges including limited sample size, seasonal variation, competition, changing consumer preferences, cost constraints, data accuracy, and limited resources. These problems, according to the author, can be solved by stating clearly the research objectives, using a mix of research methods, targeting the right audience, analysing the data effectively, implementing change based on findings, and continuously monitoring and evaluating. Market research is an important component that summarises the research findings and insights, which requires proper accountability for operational stability.

A new product is defined by Kim et al. (2016) as a product for which the company needs a new marketing strategy and in which considerable changes are conveyed but excludes any changes that may need simple promotions. New product development, according to Kim et al., is the

transformation of a market opportunity into a product as a result of the integrative coupling of market assumptions with technological possibilities.

The Product Development and Management Association (PDMA) (2016) defined product development as an overall process of strategy, concept generation, organisation, product and marketing plan creation and evaluation, and commercialisation of a product. This means that product development is a process that begins with opportunity identification and ends with a set of information that adds value to customers and brings returns to an enterprise. The product development procedure involves the activities carried out when designing, developing, and introducing new products.

A new product that is introduced into the market evolves over a series of stages, starting with a preliminary product concept or idea that is assessed, developed, tested, and introduced into the market (Safety Culture Content Team, 2024). This series of actions can also be seen as a sequence of information gathering and assessment stages. Product development cannot be successful if a diversification of business risk strategy is not incorporated into the process.

Product Development Strategy and Operational Stability of Bakery industries

Any bakery company that does not involve food experts and researchers who work with innovative concepts to bring up new ideas in creating trendy bakery products is planning to wind up. Product development in the context of bakeries, according to Safety Culture Content Team (2024), refers to the process of creating new and innovative food products for customers to purchase. This includes developing new recipes for baked goods, experimenting with different ingredients and flavour combinations, and testing new production methods. The goal of product development, as maintained by Hassan and Ahmed (2022), is to create unique and desirable products that will attract customers and drive sales. Hassan and Ahmed further posited that product innovation and reformation are essential in the highly competitive bakery company and in areas where expertise is widely appreciated. Kim et al. (2016) added that bakery confidential services provide support at all parts of the product development chain—from brainstorming product concepts and converting ideas to prototypes, to refining trial products and producing samples for market testing, advising on pilot production, and scaling up for manufacturing. Kim et al. (2016) further stated that product developers handle designing and creating new products as well as maintaining or updating existing ones.

The objective of product development from a business standpoint is to cultivate, maintain, and increase a company's market share by satisfying consumer demand. From a customer's standpoint, it is to ensure value in the product as a quality good or service. Developing a new product, according to Safety Culture Content Team (2024), is important because it provides a means of targeting new markets, increasing market share, selling more, and increasing revenue streams. Meanwhile, redesigning existing products enables costs to be cut, margins to be increased, and ultimately more profits to be made. The purpose of product development is to introduce or make improvements in bakery business offerings that are a benefit to customers. Mbithi and Nurrani (2021) opined that this, in turn, will help a bakery business to become more successful as customers will want to continue to be served by the bakery company.

Variations in ingredients, equipment, or baking techniques can lead to inconsistencies in the final product. On the other hand, Hughes further stated that finding high-quality ingredients at affordable prices can be a challenge for bakery industries, and changes in suppliers or availability of key ingredients can impact the product development process. In terms of shelf-life and freshness, Owuor (2015) opined that bakery products are often perishable and have a limited shelf-life. Developing products that stay fresh for an optimal amount of time without the use of preservatives can be challenging. In terms of customer preferences, Avila and

Nurrani (2021) suggested that understanding and adapting to changing consumer preferences, dietary trends, and demands for healthier options can be a challenge for a bakery company.

Developing products that cater to a diverse customer base while maintaining the core offerings can be a balancing act. In terms of competition, Reguia (2014) stipulated that the bakery company is highly competitive, with new trends and innovations constantly emerging. Keeping up with competitors and staying ahead of the curve in product development can be a challenge for bakery industries. Meanwhile, Oluwakemi (2017) stated that meeting food safety and labeling regulations can be a challenge for a bakery company, especially when developing new products or using new ingredients. Ensuring compliance with regulations while maintaining product quality and taste is crucial. In terms of cost management, Stephen (2017) asserted that developing new products can be costly, especially when experimenting with new ingredients or techniques. Balancing the cost of product development with potential returns and profitability can be a challenge for bakery companies. In effect, as the new product develops, management becomes more and more well-informed and certain about the product and can evaluate and reevaluate its preliminary decision to undertake development or launch.

To make product development successful, there should be synergy between the research and development, engineering, manufacturing, finance, marketing, and purchasing departments. The marketing department first has to make an evaluation about the new product, and then a cross-functional team created for the new product has to come into the scene for development of the new product (Stone and Desmond, 2017). The product development procedure consists of the activities carried out when designing and introducing new products. Following this process of information gathering and evaluation can lead to improved new product decisions on the part of firms by limiting the level of risk and minimizing the resources committed to products that eventually fail. The product development process differs from industry to industry and from firm to firm. Indeed, it should be adapted to each firm in order to meet specific company resources and needs.

Operational Stability

According to Hays (2023), operational stability has to do with the physical requirements of running bakery companies. It describes how they organise day-to-day activities, achieve their tasks, and earn a profit.

Methodology

The study made use of a descriptive survey. This design helps researchers identify characteristics in their target market or particular population. These characteristics in the population sample can be identified, observed, and measured to guide decisions. The population of the study comprised 439 managers and sales representatives made up of 154 managers and 285 sales representatives in the 86 bakeries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

A sample of 344 respondents was drawn from the population of 439 staff in the 86 registered bakery companies. In order that each company be represented. This represents 78.5% of the population. The sample size was made up of 86 managers and 258 sales representatives. The sample was selected using purposeful and simple random sampling techniques. The justification for using 78.5% of the population is that when the population is small, it is generally better to use a larger percentage of the population as the sample size to ensure adequate representation and reliable results.

Data were collected through primary and secondary sources. In the primary sources, the researcher developed a structured instrument titled: Market Expansion and Operational

Stability of Bakery Questionnaire (MEOSBCQ) for data collection. This instrument was developed by the researcher based on the research questions guiding the study. In the secondary sources, data were gathered from textbooks, internet sources, journals, among others. Simple linear regression was used to answer the research questions and to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

Findings and Discussion

Research Questions 1: What is the influence of market research on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Regression analysis result of market research on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria N = 344

Model	R.	R-Square	Adjusted R - Square
Market research	.098	.078	7.8%
Operational Stability			

Table 1 result shows the influence of market research on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The analysis reveals a correlation (R) of .078, which indicates 7.8% of the variance. The R² of .078 indicates that there is a strong influence of market research on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Research Questions 2

What is the influence of product development on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

Table 4:3: Regression analysis result of product development on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria N = 344

Model	R.	R-Square	Adjusted R - Square
Product development	.074	.079	7.9%
Operational Stability			

Table 2 result shows the influence of product development on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The analysis reveals a correlation (R) of .079, which indicates 74% of the variance. The R² of .079 indicates strong influence. The R² of .079 indicates that the independent variable accounts for 7.9% of the variance of the dependent variable. This implies that there is a strong influence of product development on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant influence of market research on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Summary of regression analysis on market research on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria N = 344

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	P-value	Remark
Regression	3.896	1	3.896	3.976	.047.	Sig
Residual.	400.7780	343				
Total.	517.780	344				

Model.	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t.	Sig
	B.	Std Error	Beta		
(Constant)	20.263	.955		21.210	0.45
Total market research	.066	.033	.098	1.994	.047

Significant @ .05 level of significance

The result presented on Table 3 shows the regression analysis of linear regression, F, 3976, p-.047. Since the p-value was less than the significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant influence of market research on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, market research accounted for approximately 66%, which explained variability in operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This implies that for every unit increase in management ability to use market research as marketing strategy in their operations, they increase operational stability in the companies. This means that 66% variation in management task was as a result of proper use of market research in their operations. Therefore, there is a significant influence of market research on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant influence of product development on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Summary of regression analysis on product development on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria N = 344

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	p-value	Remark
Regression	.257	1	.257	.228	.0063	Sig
Residual	461.417	343	1.128			
Total	461675	344				

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t.	Sig
	B	Std Error	Beta		
(Constant)	17.439	1.306		13.349	0.15
Total product development	.075	.021	.024	.478	.0063

Not Significant @ .05 level of significance

The result presented in Table 4 shows the regression analysis of linear regression, F, .228, p-values .0063. Since the p-value was less than the significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant influence of product development on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, product development accounted for approximately 75%, which explained strong variability in operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This implies that for every unit increase of the management's ability to use product development in order to measure its effectiveness, management increases product development. This means that 75% variation in management task was as a result of proper product development during bakery operations to drive sufficient and good market share. Therefore, there is a significant influence of product development on operational stability of bakery in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Market Research and Operational Stability of Bakery Industries

The result revealed a strong and significant influence of market research on operational stability of bakery industries. The influence of having a clearly identified target market, having a unique selling proposition from their competitors, looking into current trends to leverage on product, determining who the potential customers are, choosing research methods and being able to analyse data and other factors is strong. This finding is in agreement with Omolia and Nelson (2018) who found out that gathering and analysing information about target market, customers, competitors and other relevant factors were tools for business sustainability.

Product Development and Operational Stability of Industries

The result revealed that all items on product development had strong and significant influence on operational stability of bakery industries. This finding is in line with the position of Omolia and Nelson (2018) who found out that developing new products helps bakeries to increase their market share and customer base. This implies that management of bakery should really pay attention to these factors, as failure to consider product development has led to the closure of many bakery companies.

Conclusion

Market expansion has moderate and significant influence on operational stability of bakery industries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Market expansion is the foundation on which market share depends; achieving operational stability, such industries must identify potential new markets, understand the target customers' needs, determine how products meet the needs of the consumers, engage in product development, among others.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were:

1. Owners and managers of bakery industries should endeavor to provide the necessary tools and facilities needed to achieve business improvement and expansion, which is the ultimate goal of bakery industries. It will help bakery industries to have operational stability and competitive advantage over others.
2. Product should be properly developed to have good market share.
3. There should be proper market research in order to have business sustainability.

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